

Examining Long run Relationship among Health Status, Health Expenditure and Income in India: An Empirical Analysis with Co-integration Approach and Error Correction Mechanism

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Abstract

From the early 1990s, it has been seen that economic growth and health status are interdependent. Keeping this in mind this chapter attempts to examine the economic impact on health sector by dealing with various issues pertaining to the association among health status, health expenditure and income. Taking time series data from 1961 to 2013 this chapter tries to find out whether public health care spending is considered as “care” or “cure”. With the help of co-integration approach and error correction mechanism this chapter examines whether any long run relationship prevails between public health care expenditure and income; between health status measured by Infant Survival Rate and public health care spending; lastly between health status and income. During this short-run healthcare expenditure-income analysis some interesting insights into health policy and health financing emerges which reflects that health care needs are regarded as normal as well as necessary commodity in India. The present study finds a very positive impact of economic reforms and globalization on the relationship between public healthcare spending and income. It is observed that long-run relationship exists between public health care expenditure and income for the time period from 1961 to 2013. But any long-run relationship between infant survival rate and health expenditure as well as income for the same period is not found. The present empirical study also establishes that health related investments must be much higher in developing country like India to augment economic growth and ensure equity.

Key Words: Public Health Care Expenditure, Engel’s coefficients of elasticity, Cure, Long-run relationship, Error correction mechanism

Introduction

From the early 1990s, the interdependence between economic growth and health status is observed. The levels of human capital (comprising health, education and skill) ensures Sustained economic growth. Better growth outcomes are registered by better health. Ensuring a long, healthy and fulfilling life of each and every individual is the main challenge of 21st century to ease out the process of their participation in the various activities of their community. With a view to promote sustainable development, poverty alleviation and eradication of other human deprivation were among the major targets of Millennium Development Goals in 2000 signed by 189 countries. India has wide range of health and socio economic diversity across the states. The correlation among health status, health expenditure and income is of paramount importance in India. Populations live better and longer lives and possess good health with the process of sustained economic growth. Firstly, with the rise of economic growth, percapita income rises. A part of this increased income is spent for the consumption of nutritious foods. Well nutrition, increases life expectancy through which health responds to income growth [Fogel 1997]. Secondly, medical science is improved by technological progress which fuels the economic growth [Rosen 1993, Morand 2005]. Economic growth of a country is affected by its health status through multiple channels. Improved health situation generates higher output along with education and technological advancement. Health is treated as one of the prime

factors of human capital for formulation of endogenous growth models [Barro 1991, Mankiw et al 1992, Thomas et al 1997, Bloom et al 2001]. Central to these long-term growth models is the idea that technology is endogenous to the growth process [Romer 1986, Lucas 1988]. Higher human capital investment leads to higher educational attainment and better socio economic status of health which augments growth. On the other hand, larger investments in human capital is encouraged by higher life expectancy at birth leading to rise in per capita income. Stark [1995] offers the mechanism of intergenerational transfer of assets through which longer life expectancy leads to larger investments on human capital. Higher educational level and better health status evolve systematically in accordance with the economic development of an economy. Availability of public health care facilities helps the poor toward releasing resources for other investments. The interlinkage between health and socio-economic status is one of the major areas of today’s research findings in health economics. A positive relationship between socio-economic status and health has been observed across the countries in the world at different time periods[Berkman 1988, Marmot et al 1991, Feinstein 1993, Deaton et al 2001, Deaton 2003]. Education could induce better health behaviors or income. Healthier populations generates higher labor productivity, through creation of physically more energetic and mentally more robust labour force and reduction of suffering from illness of the workers which in turn reduces absenteeism in the work place.

As levels of education and health rise, rate of investment also tends to increase as implied by the human capital component. These components evolve systematically in accordance with the levels of economic development. Therefore, such changes lead to raise the rate of investment. Thus, accumulation low levels of human capital impedes competitiveness and acts as constraint to economic development. Appropriate policy formulation is needed for better understanding of mechanisms in the context of the process of human capital formations to ensure sustained economic growth.

Objective of the Study-Associated Research Questions

The interlinkage among health, health care investment and income helps us to understand the causality between income and demand side of health. In the context of health policy and health financing issues my present study of health care expenditure and income analysis is expected to provide some interesting insights.

During the course of this study a number of research questions have been arisen which are to be examined such as –

- 1) Whether the public healthcare spending is considered as “care” (denoted as luxury good) or “cure” (being a necessary good)?
- 2) Whether any long run relationship prevails between public health care expenditure and income; between health status measured by Infant Survival Rate (ISR) and public health care spending; lastly between health status and income.

The Data and Methodology

The data on public health care are drawn from National Accounts Statistics (NAS). The department of statistics, planning commission published every year data on household health care expenditure –

Table 1: Engel’s Coefficients of Elasticity of household expenditure on health care (1960-61 to 2012-13)

Elasticity of	To	Coefficient	t-Value	R-Squared	DW Statistics
PCPubHCE	PCGNP	0.386	19.39	0.880	0.131

Note : The above tables are formed based on National Time Series Data on public final expenditure in real prices(1993-94 base year).

Variables, their notation and definition:

PCPub HCE : Per Capita Public Health Care Expenditure.

PCGNP : Per Capita Gross National Product.

Longrun Association between PCPubHCE and PCGNP

Table 2- Unit root checking for PCPubHCE time series (Period: 1961-2013)

		With Intercept	With Trend and Intercept
Level	ADF	3.3116 0.7941(with log)	0.0160 -2.6249(with log)
	Critical Value at 5% level of significance	-2.9190	-3.4987

private and public final consumption expenditure based on estimations done by National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO) in National Accounts Statistics. The per capita Gross National Product (PCGNP) of India over the periods from 1960-61 to 2012-13 was collected from Reserve Bank of India Bulletin (various issues), NAS. The health care expenditure as well as GNP is measured in real (at 1993-94 prices) per capita terms. Data source of Infant mortality rate (IMR) is sample registration system, Govt. of India, from which ISR have been calculated. The variables are measured in natural logarithm. Here income is measured by percapita GNP (PCGNP) and health expenditure is measured by per capita public healthcare expenditure (PCPubHCE).

Income elasticity of public health care expenditure over the period from 1961-2013

With the estimation of Engel’s coefficients of elasticity, I have tried in my present study to find the answer of first question. how does Govt. investment in health care change over the periods given a similar change in income levels is obtained by the value of Engel’s coefficients of elasticity of two concerned variables. There are various alternative specifications of the equations which can be considered to estimate the Engel coefficient. The double logarithmic equation is specified as,

$$\ln(\text{PCPubHCE}) = A + B \ln(\text{PCGNP}) + e \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

B in the above equation is interpreted as the Engel coefficients of elasticity.

A is intercept term and e is the error term.

Using double logarithmic of equation (1), coefficients of elasticity are estimated here and they are given in Table 1. Estimates are made considering per capita expenditures.

Tests of Stationarity

The study involves the extensive use of time series techniques. The time series for PCPubHCE and PCGNP have been subject to tests for stationarity for which Augmented Dicky-Fuller Method has been adopted

Cointegration

I have used Engle-Granger (EG) approach for this purpose.

Table 3- Unit root checking for PCGNP time series (Period: 1961-2013)

		With Intercept	With Trend and Intercept
Level	ADF	1.0091 2.3861(with log)	0.7024 -3.3343(with log)
	Critical Value at 5% level of significance	-2.9190	-3.4987

Table :4 Testing Stationarity of the variables with and without log

Variables measured in various forms	ADF Values: With intercept	ADF Values: With trend and intercept
PCPubHCE	3.3116	0.0160
Δ PCPubHCE	-3.6087	-5.2640
ln(PCPubHCE)	0.7941	-2.6249
Δln(PCPubHCE)	-7.6612	-7.9592
PCGNP	1.0091	0.7024
Δ PCGNP	-0.0296	-1.6672
Δ ² PCGNP	-7.0229	-7.1682
ln PCGNP	2.3861	-3.3343
Δ(ln PCGNP)	-4.0512	-4.8183
ISR	0.2408	-1.7758
Δ ISR	-5.6175	-5.6437
ln(ISR)	0.1355	-1.7599
Δ ln(ISR)	-5.6790	-5.6765

Notes: 5% Mackinnon critical value for the rejection of hypothesis: -2.9190(with intercept); -3.4987(with trend and intercept): From the table 4 it is found that PCPubHCE is stationary at its first differenced series and PCGNP at its 2nd differenced series. PCGNP ~I(2) and PCPubHCE ~ I(1). The log values of all the variables are stationary at their first differenced series, ie, ln(PCPubHCE) ~ I(1); ln(PCGNP) ~ I(1); lnISR) ~ I(1)

Now I have checked the stationarity of the estimated equilibrium errors of the equation

$$\ln(\text{PCPubHCE}_t) = \alpha + \beta \ln(\text{PCGNP}_t) + e_t \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

The longrun estimated equilibrium relationship, or the cointegrating regression is the following.

$$\ln(\text{PCPubHCE}_t) = 0.432 + 0.4539 \ln(\text{PCGNP}_t) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

$$t \quad [8.234] \quad [65.137]$$

$$R^2 = 0.988, DW = 1.860$$

Using [1, -0.432, -0.4539] e_t is estimated and saved. ADF value of e_t is -4.913, where 5% critical value for rejection of the hypothesis is -1.947. We accept e_t is stationary, meaning thus the log values of the variables PCPubHCE and PCGNP are cointegrated or there exists a longrun relationship between these two variables.

Next I check whether there exists a longrun relationship between the log values of the variables

ISR and PCPubHCE, taking the former as dependant variable.

$$\ln(\text{ISR}_t) = \alpha + \beta \ln(\text{PCPubHCE}_t) + e_t \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

The longrun estimated equilibrium relationship, or the cointegrating regression is the following.

$$\ln(\text{ISR}_t) = 6.5827 + 0.0533 \ln(\text{PCPubHCE}_t) \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

$$t \quad [917.322] \quad [29.887]$$

$$R^2 = 0.956, DW = 1.1828$$

ADF value of e_t is 3.4985, where 5% critical value for rejection of the hypothesis is -1.949. we accept e_t is nonstationary, meaning thus log values of the variables ISR and PCPubHCE are not cointegrated. Finally, we check the longrun relationship between the log values of the variables ISR and PCGNP.

$$\ln(\text{ISR}_t) = \alpha + \beta \ln(\text{PCGNP}_t) + e_t \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

The longrun estimated equilibrium relationship, or the cointegrating regression is the following.

$$\ln(\text{ISR}_t) = 6.604 + 0.024 \ln(\text{PCGNP}_t) \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

$$t \quad [1159.74] \quad [33.875]$$

$$R^2 = 0.965, DW = 0.677$$

ADF value of e_t is -1.617, where 5% critical value for rejection of the hypothesis is -1.949. we accept e_t is nonstationary, meaning thus log values of the variables ISR and PCGNP are not cointegrated or

there does not exist a longrun relationship between these two variables.

Cointegration: the estimation of the error correction models (ECM)

'Granger representation theorem'(Granger,1986;Engle and Granger,1987) suggests, the variables exhibiting longrun relation may be in disequilibrium in short run, with the disturbances being the equilibrating error e_t . This shortrun disequilibrium is described by an 'error correction model'(ECM) introduced by Sargan(1964).

Estimating an Error Correction Model Between log Values of PCPubHCE and PCGNP:

Log values of PCPubHCE and PCGNP both variable are cointegrated of order (1,1).

Step1

Summary and conclusion:

In this paper, the longrun relationship between health status(determined by infant survival rate ISR),health expenditure(public); and health status and income have been analyzed in a bi-variate framework using original data set as well as longitudinal data for 53 years from 1961 to 2013. With the help of the application of cointegration approach it has been found that the log values of the variables infant survival rate and public healthcare spending and income – all are integrated of order 1. But I have not found any longrun relationship between log values of infant survival rate and public healthcare spending ; log values of infant survival rate and income as estimated e series of the relevant equation has not come out to be stationary in either case. So it is clear from our present analysis that even though the two series is integrated of the same

References:

1. Barro, R.J.(1991): 'Economic Growth in a Cross Section of Countries', Quarterly Journal of Economics, 196, 2nd May, pp. 407-443.
2. Berkman, Lisa F. (1988): 'The Changing and Heterogeneous Nature of Aging and Longevity: A Social and Biochemical Perspective', in Annual Review of gerontology and Geriatrics, 8, ed. George L. Maddox and M. Powell Lawton, pp.37-68.
3. Bloom, D.E., Canning, D. and E. Sevilla, J.(2001): The Effect of Health on Economic Growth: Theory and Evidence, Cambridge: National Bureau of Economic Research, Working Paper 8587, pp. 26
4. Deaton, Angus and Christina Paxon.(2001): 'Mortality, Education, Income, and Inequality among American Cohorts', in Themes in the Economics of Aging. David Wise (ed.), Chicago University Press for NBER, Paper 7140.
5. Deaton, Angus.(2003): 'Health, Inequality and Economic Development', Journal of Economic Literature, Vol. XLI March, pp. 113-158.

From the cointegrating regression estimated in equation(3),or

$$\ln(\text{PCPubHCE}_t) = 0.432 + 0.4539 \ln(\text{PCGNP}_t) + e_t$$

t [8.234] [65.137]

$R^2 = 0.988, DW = 1.860$

We get the residuals, e_t .

Step 2

One version of an estimated error correction model is the following.

$$\Delta \ln(\text{PCPubHCE}_t) = 0.0255 + 0.1736 \Delta \ln(\text{PCGNP}_t) - 0.952 e_{t-1} + \dots + e_t \quad (8)$$

t [1.365] [0.929] [-6.876]

$R^2 = 0.500, DW = 1.975$

Here, the t-statistic 0.929 is not significant .So,we cannot argue anything regarding the short-run adjustment.

order,it is not necessarily true that they will be cointegrated or will exhibit a longrun relationship. However a long-run relationship between public health care expenditure and income has been found which suggest that Government should increase its investment in health care in accordance with the economic growth of India. Moreover, public investment in health care is treated as necessity (cure) rather than luxury(care) requirement. Inception of Research on investment in health or healthcare expenditure in India is very limited. But the importance of such research is being realized nowadays, especially in the area of gradually diminishing public budgets for health care and formulation of effective as well as alternative policies towards financing healthcare spending. A good number of effective public policies should be formulated based on the research evidence.

6. Feinstein, Jonathan.(1993): 'The Relationship between Socio-economic Status and Health: A Review of Literature', Milbank Quarterly, 71(2), pp. 279-322.
7. Fogel, R.W.(1994): The Relevance of Malthus for the Study of Mortality Today: Long Run Influences on Health, Mortality, Labor Force Participation and Population Growth, Historical Paper No.54, National Bureau of Economic Research, March, pp. 36
8. Granger, C.(1981): 'Some Properties of Time Series Data and their use in Econometric Model Specification', Journal of Econometrics, 16. pp. 121-130.
9. Lopez-Casasnovas, G., Berta Rivera., and Luis Currais(2005): 'The Role Health Plays in Economic Growth' in Health and Economic Growth: Findings and Policy Implications, edited by Lopez-Casasnovas, G., Berta Rivera, MIT Press, MIT Cambridge, Massachusetts.
10. Lucas, R.E.(1988): 'On the Mechanics of Economic Development', Journal of Monetary Economics, 22: pp.3-42.

11. Mankiw, N.G., Romer, D. and Weil, D.(1992): 'A Contribution to the Empirics of Economic Growth', *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, May, pp.407-37.
12. Romer, P.(1986): Increasing Returns and Long-Run Growth, *Journal of Political Economy*, 94 (5), pp. 1002-1037.
13. Rosen, G.(1993): *A History of Public Health*, Baltimore, John Hopkins University Press.
14. Thomas, D. and J. Strauss.(1997): 'Health and Wages: Evidence on Men and Women in Urban Brazil', *Journal of Econometrics*, 77.
15. Stark, Oded.(1995): *Altruism and Beyond: An Economic Analysis of Transfers and Exchanges within Families and Groups*, Cambridge University Press.
16. Tilak, J. B. J. (2002): "Elasticity of Household Expenditure on Education in Rural India", *South Asia Economic Journal*, 3(2), pp. 217-226.